

Documentation of results

Constellation analysis of organic sugar beet farming in northeastern Germany with a focus on robotic weed control

Developed in the project Uckerbots: Concept and technology development for swarm robotics for the expansion of organic sugar beet cultivation in the Uckermark region

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Abbreviations

CA	Constellation analysis
HNEE	Eberswalde University for Sustainable Development
IHP	Leibniz Institute for High Performance Microelectronics
ZALF	Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research

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1. Objective of the documentation of results

This document presents the results of a constellation analysis (CA), which was developed in the Uckerbots research project¹. For a better understanding, the bridging concept CA is briefly introduced with references to further literature (Chapter 2). Afterwards, the Uckerbots research project is outlined in order to explain the context and objectives of the CA (Chapter 3). The procedure and results of the CA are then presented in more detail (Chapter 4).

2. Constellation analysis as a bridging concept

CA is an interdisciplinary bridging concept that can be used, among other things, for strategy development in sustainability and technology research. It was developed at the Center Technology and Society at Technische Universität Berlin (Schön et al. 2007) and has already been used for various scientific issues (Bruns and Ohlhorst 2011; Ohlhorst and Schön 2015; Schäfer and Kröger 2016).

The CA is intended to facilitate collaboration in inter- and transdisciplinary teams and in particular knowledge integration. As part of the CA, a central question is formulated and relevant actors and elements are first identified and then analyzed with regard to their relations. A visualization illustrates the relations between actors and elements. This simplifies the communication between the collaborating transdisciplinary actors with different perspectives and expertise. The mapping of a CA is carried out in steps that involve actors (possibly with varying degrees of involvement) who can make a relevant contribution based on their expertise or the extent to which they are affected. Schön et al. (2007, p. 21ff) formulate some rules for joint mapping process. These include, among other aspects, that all actors have an equal opportunity to comment on the graphic and to be heard.

Figure 1 Visualization of forms of actors, elements and relations

In the collaborative mapping process, an attempt is made to create a figure that is as complete as possible while maintaining a degree of clarity. A distinction is made between four types of elements: social actors, systems of signs, technical and natural elements. These are shown in Figure 1. Social actors can be individuals or groups, networks or organizations. Systems of signs include norms, regulations, ideologies and laws. Technical elements can be specific applications such as an app or general technical concepts (e.g. hardware or software). Natural elements include materials and resources. Conceptually element types and actors are considered equally – the analysis demonstrates the relevance of specific social actors, systems of signs, natural and technical elements.

The developers of the CA method propose to map various forms of relations between elements and actors. Four types of notations that were used for the following results can be seen in Figure 1. The

¹ More information on the project at <https://region40.de/portfolio-item/uckerbots/>

visualization is supplemented by a descriptive text. The latter can contain explanations, additions and sources.

3. The Uckerbots project and objectives of the CA

The project „Uckerbots: Concept and technology development for swarm robotics for the expansion of organic sugar beet cultivation in the Uckermark region“ is a transdisciplinary research project to develop a robot for weed control in organic sugar beet cultivation. The project was initiated in response to the needs of organic farmers in northeastern Germany. Farmers would like to grow sugar beet, but do not yet have a suitable strategy for organic weed control.

The project is managed by the Eberswalde University for Sustainable Development (HNEE). The agronomists at HNEE are testing the robot on their agricultural test fields and in cooperation with farmers. Another project partner is the Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF) interested in the effects of the new technology on biodiversity. The robotics company Zauberzeug GmbH develops the robot and responds to test reports from HNEE. In collaboration with the Leibniz Institute for Innovative Microelectronics (IHP), a swarm approach is to be implemented that connects several robots together. The authors are involved in the project on behalf of the Center Technology and Society at the Technische Universität Berlin to analyze the transdisciplinary cooperation and changes in agricultural practices in connection to the use of the robot. There is also ongoing communication with a representative of the local beet processing company and several interested farmers.

The aim of the CA is to create a common understanding of the key obstacles to the regional establishment of organic sugar beet farming. Strategies are also to be developed to resolve these barriers.

4. Results: Descriptive text and mapping

4.1 Introduction and procedure

The constellation maps the requirements of organic sugar beet farming in northeastern Germany and deals with the question of how the regional production of organic sugar can be established. It focuses on strategies for weed control and the role of robotics. The potential future use of the Uckerbot is particularly considered. For this purpose, we have mapped a constellation of the status quo and a target constellation of possible future developments that would contribute to the establishment of organic sugar beet cultivation in northeastern Germany. The two authors of this report have prepared an initial constellation. This was based on project reports and publications from the preceding project zUckerrübe² (Steinherr 2021; Steinherr et al. 2023b, 2023a). In addition, protocols from the regular project meetings between May 2022 and September 2023 of the zUckerrübe and Uckerbots projects were used.

In a second phase, the prepared constellation was discussed with the agronomists at HNEE and the technology developers of Zauberzeug. The graphic was adapted to the feedback. Six interviews were then conducted. Five farmers, a representative of the local beet processing company, and a representative of a local business development office (from the food science cluster) were interviewed. The constellation graphic was iteratively adjusted after each interview.

² The full title of the project is: “zUckerrübe - Cultivation method development using innovative field robotics, UAS (unmanned aerial system) & practical research for organic sugar beet cultivation in the Uckermark region”.

4.2 Status quo constellation of organic sugar beet farming

The status quo constellation of organic sugar beet farming in northeastern Germany is presented below. Figure 2 shows the mapped constellation. The center of the constellation with the most important elements is located on the main circle in the center-left, which also contains the title of the constellation. Two circles branch off from it. The upper circle focuses on (technological) weed control, while the lower circle shows aspects of agricultural competence development. The elements of these three circles and their relations are now presented in more detail. Actors and elements that appear in the graphic are underlined in the text.

Figure 2 Status quo constellation of organic sugar beet farming in northeastern Germany

The status quo constellation depicts the current state of organic sugar beet cultivation in northeastern Germany. The main center-left circle in Figure 2 is the first one to be described.

- The conditions for sugar beet cultivation in northeastern Germany are favorable. The rich soils are well suited to the specialty crop of sugar beets. In addition, the sugar factory in Anklam is planning to establish an organic sugar beet campaign³, i.e. to process not only conventionally but also organically grown sugar beets in the long term. Their first organic sugar beet campaign took place in 2023.
- The starting point for the organic cultivation of sugar beet in northeastern Germany is the assumption of a high demand for organic sugar from the organic retail trade in Berlin as well as from the beverage industry and regional processing companies. In order for the beet campaign to be economically viable for the sugar factory, a certain harvest quantity must be achieved. The cultivation of sugar beet is expanded if it is profitable for farmers. In principle, the (organic) cultivation of sugar beet enables high profit margins with a successful harvest. This is visualized by the close proximity of the elements sugar beet and economic profitability.

³ Sugar beet campaign refers to the processing of sugar beet in sugar factories.

- The key challenge in sugar beet cultivation is weed control. Sugar beet develops comparatively slowly at the beginning and growth is therefore at risk from harmful weeds. This challenge is emphasized by the conflictual relation arrow between the elements of sugar beet and weed control.

The weed removal element connects the main circle with another circle at the top right. The latter maps the relevant actors and elements in weed control:

- Conventional farmers use chemical-synthetic crop protection and machine hoes.
- Organic farmers also control weeds between the beet rows with a machine hoe but need an alternative to pesticides for the weeds in the row.
- In the past, weeds in the row were removed manually by seasonal workers in organic farming. However, it is becoming increasingly difficult to find seasonal workers due to unfavorable working conditions and low wages. In addition, the costs of manual weed control are relatively high for farmers. This difficulty is again marked by a conflictual relation arrow.
- Alternatively, technical solutions can be adopted. For example, farmers are already using first robotic technology such as the Farmdroid robot for sowing and weeding. Technologies that are not based on robotics, such as a weed puller, are also already in use. Other robotic solutions are still undergoing further development.
- However, current robotic solutions such as the Farmdroid robot have problems with heterogeneous, uneven ground and slopes, which are frequent in northeastern Germany. In addition, even after the use of the Farmdroid robot, weeds that grow close to the beet remain to be removed manually. These problem areas are indicated by the question mark next to the elements weed control technologies and uneven grounds.
- In response to these challenges, the start-up Zauberzeug is developing a prototype of a weed control robot, the Uckerbot, in cooperation with the other members of the Uckerbot project team. The Uckerbot is equipped with several cameras that detect sugar beets and weeds. An algorithm based on artificial intelligence evaluates the images and distinguishes weeds from sugar beets. On this basis, the Uckerbot then weeds the plants that were not identified as sugar beet. Compared to alternative technologies, the Uckerbot is a small and lightweight device. It is intended to be particularly suitable for the use on uneven ground in northeastern Germany. The Uckerbot has been continuously developed since 2021 based on feedback from farmers and from the tests by employees of the Eberswalde University for Sustainable Development. The current goal is to establish a robotic swarm technology, i.e. to use several interconnected robots in the fields at the same time.
- Agricultural machinery dealers and contractors currently play a key role in the sale, rental and use of weed control technologies and are expected to continue to do so in the future.

However, the harvest success depends not only on the use of weed control technology, but on the interplay of several factors. These factors mainly relate to farming competences and are shown in the third circle at the bottom right.

- Farmers need to make the right decisions at the right time (timing) and remove weeds during the critical phase of sugar beet cultivation, when the sugar beet is just emerging. Sugar beet cultivation requires particular attention in this critical phase.
- Other aspects such as rainfall and soil conditions also have an impact on harvest success and need to be considered in the cultivation strategies. Furthermore, well-designed crop rotations and cultivation techniques can have a positive effect on harvest yields.
- The question mark indicates the existing uncertainties regarding the choice of technology, timing, cultivation techniques and climatic conditions.
- As an institutional actor, the local sugar processing factory and its cultivation advisors provide various agricultural extension services for farmers. This helps to fill gaps that arise due to the lack of agricultural extension services in Brandenburg (compared to other federal states). The sugar factory is in close contact with the organic farmers through the extension services and economic ties.
- In summary, three factors are central to the establishment of organic sugar beet cultivation in northeastern Germany. First, the economic viability of sugar beet cultivation and processing must be ensured. Second, this requires a suitable technology for weed control and third, appropriate knowledge on the use of the technology and other cultivation aspects.

4.3 Target constellation of organic sugar beet cultivation in 2030

The target constellation looks 5-7 years into the future and addresses the problems of the status quo constellation. Once again, the circle with the most important elements is at the center. This circle takes up the three core challenges of the current constellation and identifies three strategies, visualized by grey boxes. First, solutions for weed control have been developed, second, consulting and advisory services have been expanded and third, this has resulted in increased growing capacities of organic sugar beet. This enabled the establishment of organic sugar beet farming and processing in northeastern Germany. The three strategies are explained below.

Weed control, which used to be challenging, is now carried out reliably with the help of technology. This is represented by elements in the upper center circle.

- This has enabled to reduce risks and production costs.
- Reliable weed control was made possible by the further development and introduction of new innovative weed control technologies, which are used in combination with the well-established machine hoe.
- Manual weed control is carried out much less frequently than in the past and mainly to remove weeds that remain after the use of weed control technology.
- Zauberzeug has brought the swarm-intelligent Uckerbots to the market and is gradually handing over the production of the robots to a manufacturing company.

- Initially, pioneer farms tested the Uckerbots and contributed to their improvement. Some farmers also use the Uckerbot in combination with the Farmdroid sowing and weeding robot. First, the Farmdroid sows and weeds and then the Uckerbot removes the remaining weeds that grow close to the beet.

Figure 3 Target constellation of organic sugar beet farming with robotic weed control in 2030

Some success conditions influence whether the swarm-intelligent Uckerbots become established in practice. This is described by elements and their relations, which are arranged on another circle at the top right. The establishment of the Uckerbots becomes more probable if:

- The Uckerbots are used in other cultures. As the Uckerbots are only used for a short period of time in in sugar beet farming, they could be used in other crops, increasing their profitability. However, the high profit margin in sugar beet cultivation, which justifies higher costs for weed removal (e.g. through the use of a robot), must also be taken into account. This may differ in the cultivation of other crops. Considerations regarding the wear and tear of the robot and the maintenance costs also play a role here.
- Research, investment and business funding support the further development or acquisition of the Uckerbot.
- In addition to organic farmers, individual conventional farmers also use Uckerbots. In conventional cultivation, however, there is currently less incentive to find a weed removal technology due to the success of weed removal with pesticides.
- The openness to technology is increasing and more and more farmers are taking the leap into this new technology. At the same time, Zauberzeug remains open-minded and continues to develop the Uckerbot even after its market launch in order to solve any problems that arise.

The second problem regarding the **necessary competences and extension services** to deal with the interplay of different cultivation factors has also been solved.

- Established agricultural machinery dealers and newly founded start-ups take over the distribution and rental of the Uckerbots. They also offer comprehensive technical support services. These include spare parts deliveries, technical trainings and help with technical problems. If the Uckerbot has technical problems, farmers can get help quickly and easily. During the critical time period for beet cultivation, service providers are available at all hours and even at weekends. This critical phase is between April and June. Spare parts must be delivered quickly (by the next working day, e.g. by express delivery).
- Growers' associations and the Eberswalde University for Sustainable Development provide cultivation knowledge and technological expertise (agricultural extension services).
- The agricultural advisors at the sugar factory in Anklam also pass on the knowledge and cultivation expertise they have gained specifically for sugar beet farming.

Growing capacities have been increased by improving weed control technologies and cultivation knowledge.

- In particular, the reduced production costs due to the new weed control strategies guarantee economic profitability in organic sugar beet cultivation.
- As a result, farmers expanded their sugar beet cultivation and new farmers started sugar beet farming.
- This made it possible to establish organic sugar beet processing at the Anklam sugar factory.
- The organic sugar beet is now marketed in the organic food retail and processing sectors, thus generating regional value creation.

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